

Exploring Psychological Well-being and Integrated Care Approaches in Older Adults: A Quantitative and Descriptive Analysis of Key Factors in Lifelong Education

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ABSTRACT

Background: This pilot study addresses the importance of psychological and emotional well-being in older adults, focusing on the population of the Lifelong Learning University for older adults in Alicante (Spain). It investigates how various psychosocial and educational factors impact their quality of life and personal satisfaction. The aim is to identify key elements influencing the well-being of this population, with special attention to self-esteem, self-efficacy, satisfaction with personal achievements, and the integration of patient care approaches. It seeks to positively influence them through education, considering lifelong education as an integral part of a holistic care model that promotes active and healthy aging.

Methods and findings: A descriptive and quantitative analysis was conducted with a small sample size of 15 older adults, serving as a pilot test to be implemented in a second phase with over a hundred participants. A questionnaire based on Ryff's psychological well-being scale was utilized. The results indicated significant variations in well-being perception related to age and other demographic factors. A high degree of personal pride and confidence in opinions was observed, although challenges in expressing opinions and susceptibility to external convictions were also noted. Cronbach's Alpha showed moderate to low reliability, influenced by the substantial age variability causing dispersion in opinions, which is considered acceptable in studies of this nature.

Conclusion: The study underscores the significance of addressing specific aspects of psychological well-being in older adults, including self-esteem, communication skills, and the necessity for integrated care approaches. The findings highlight the importance of personalized interventions and educational strategies, which are complemented by integrative patient care techniques, to enhance the quality of life for this demographic. This integrated approach suggests a broader framework for supporting older adults, not only through targeted educational programs but also by incorporating holistic care elements that address their comprehensive health and well-being needs.

Keywords: Psychological well-being; Older adults; Self-esteem; Communication; Lifelong education

INTRODUCTION

The aging of the population is a global phenomenon that poses significant challenges and opportunities in various spheres, including education [1]. In this context, the study at the Lifelong Learning University for Older Adults in Alicante (UPUA) aims to understand the interrelation between well-being and emotions in the older adult population, especially those involved in educational programs [2]. This concept is closely related to psychological and social well-being, emphasizing the importance of social integration,

active participation, and continuous learning [3].

This research gains relevance in an era where lifelong learning has become a crucial element for the personal and social enrichment of older adults [4].

In recent decades, interest in the psychological well-being of older adults has been on the rise [5]. Various studies have explored how different aspects such as self-esteem, life satisfaction, self-efficacy, and perception of personal achievements influence the quality of life of this population [6,7]. However, there is a significant gap in

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the literature regarding how these elements interact and manifest in specific educational environments for older adults.

This research addresses this gap, examining how the education provided at the UPUA influences, or could influence, the emotional and psychological well-being of older adults. Through a detailed analysis of data collected through a well-being survey, the study aims to comprehensively describe the well-being profile of this population and evaluate the reliability of the survey used.

This study is structured around several hypotheses. The Null Hypothesis (H0) posits that there are no significant differences in self-reported levels of well-being among different categories of the sample. The Alternative Hypotheses (H1, H2, and H3) explore the existence of variations in well-being perception and the reliability of the well-being survey, respectively. These hypotheses are based on the premise that education and lifelong learning can play a vital role in the well-being of older adults.

The significance of this study lies not only in its contribution to the academic field but also in its practical implications. By identifying key factors that impact the well-being of older adults in educational contexts, specific pedagogical recommendations can be formulated to enhance the quality of life and personal satisfaction of this growing demographic.

Therefore, this study aims to fill a significant gap in the understanding of the well-being of older adults within education, providing valuable initial conclusions for educators, policymakers, and other key stakeholders in adult education. The research, along with its subsequent developments, aligns with the broader goal of optimizing the learning experience and promoting psychological well-being in the classroom, thereby contributing to the holistic enrichment of older adults.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This initial research has been configured as a descriptive and quantitative analysis, representing a preliminary phase [8]. It constitutes a segment of a more extensive inquiry that will unfold in the coming months with a significantly more diverse and broader student population, exceeding a hundred participants [9]. As the primary instrument, a questionnaire based on Ryff's psychological well-being and mood scale was employed [5,10-22]. A descriptive and frequency evaluation was conducted, integrating statistics of central tendency and dispersion, with the aim of analysing responses in relation to the various elements of the well-being scale. This analysis has focused on the distribution of responses, the identification of recurring patterns, the interpretation of the results obtained, their relevance in the context of psychological well-being, and the development of pedagogical proposals grounded in these findings.

Study sample

The study targeted older adults enrolled in online education programs offered by the Lifelong Learning University for Older Adults in Alicante (UPUA). In this pilot stage, the participation of 15 individuals from a course on the History of Spain through Poison, taught by one of the researchers, was included. Despite the small sample size, this pilot group will inform future stages, expanding the scope to include the entire student body of the UPUA (over a hundred participants).

Participation was entirely voluntary and anonymous, with no additional incentives provided. Informed consent was obtained, detailing the study's purposes, potential risks, contact information for the researchers and the institution, as well as the benefits derived from participating in the research. This procedure ensured the autonomy and protection of participants' personal data, in compliance with current data protection legislation. No specific exclusion criteria were established, aiming to create a diverse and representative sample of the target population, a fundamental aspect for the generalization and relevance of the research results.

Assessment tools

A single questionnaire, previously validated and used in educational studies, was employed as a reliable and valid instrument for assessing online students aligned with the research objectives. The application of this questionnaire, crucial in the evaluation process, was estimated to take 20 to 30 minutes and was conducted at the beginning of the classes. Each question in the questionnaire was designed to align with a specific dimension of the survey, and appropriate statistical analyses were carried out to explore relationships between these dimensions and other study variables. The chosen instrument for this purpose was the Ryff psychological well-being assessment questionnaire, as mentioned earlier [5]. This questionnaire is recognized and validated in the scientific literature, with necessary adaptations made for its suitability in the specific study context [21,23,24].

For the assessment of well-being and mood, the responses obtained through the Ryff questionnaire were utilized. Each questionnaire question was associated with a specific dimension related to well-being or mood. The treatment of responses was conducted using six-point Likert scales, ranging from 1 (completely disagree) to 6 (completely agree). In this second stage of the pilot study, the analysis focused on comparing the well-being and mood levels of participants and investigating other variables of interest for the study.

Data analysis procedure

A descriptive analysis was conducted, including the determination of measures of central tendency (mean and median) and dispersion (standard deviation and range) for each item in the survey. This analysis is crucial for assessing the quality of the collected data, encompassing the identification of missing values and atypical responses. Additionally, it provides an initial and fundamental understanding of the inherent characteristics of the obtained datasets. Similarly, Cronbach's Alpha was calculated to assess the internal consistency of the items.

In subsequent phases, the data analysis will be expanded with T-Test/ANOVA results and correlation analysis. ANOVA will be used to compare three or more groups, and Kendall's Tau-b correlations, like Spearman's Rho, will be employed. Factor analysis will also be conducted as part of the extended data analysis.

Objectives

The main purpose of this study is to explore and analyze the relationship between well-being and emotions in older adults participating in programs at the Lifelong Learning University

for Older Adults in Alicante (Spain). The goal is to identify key factors that can explain how the provided education impacts their emotional state and overall well-being. Additionally, the research aims to determine pedagogical adjustments that can enhance the quality of life and personal satisfaction of these older adults.

The specific objectives of this research are, firstly, to comprehensively describe the well-being profile of the older adult population. This will be achieved through the application of statistical analyses-including measures of central tendency and dispersion-to the data collected in the well-being survey. Secondly, the study aims to determine the reliability of the well-being survey through the use of Cronbach's Alpha, ensuring the internal consistency of the survey items. Thirdly, based on the results of the analysis, the intention is to establish a series of recommendations that can be positively implemented in classrooms to contribute to the future well-being development of older adult students.

Research hypothesis

The hypotheses formulated in this study are as follows

H0 (Null hypothesis): There are no statistically significant differences in self-reported levels of well-being when comparing different categories within the selected sample. This hypothesis suggests that, regardless of demographic variables or any other categorization applied to the sample, the perceived levels of well-being by participants do not vary significantly.

H1 (First alternative hypothesis): Moderately statistically significant differences are observed in the perception of well-being among the students participating in the study. This hypothesis proposes that, although variations in well-being perception may not be extremely pronounced, there are moderate differences that are statistically detectable.

H2 (Second alternative hypothesis): There are statistically significant differences in the perception of well-being among the students involved in the research. This hypothesis suggests that variations in self-reported levels of well-being are notable and statistically relevant among different groups or categories within the studied sample.

H3 (Third alternative hypothesis): The internal consistency

Table 2: The means and standard deviations of the items statistics.

	Mean	Standard deviation	N
Age	26.000	0.73679	15
GENDER	16.000	0.50709	15
1. When I review the history of my life, I am content with how things have turned out.	44.667	0.99043	15
2. I often feel lonely because I have few close friends with whom to share my concerns.	30.667	1.62422	15
3. I am not afraid to express my opinions, even when they differ from the majority of people.	42.000	1.47358	15
4. I worry about how other people evaluate the choices I have made in my life.	23.333	1.04654	15
5. I find it difficult to steer my life toward a path that satisfies me	28.000	1.56753	15
6. I enjoy making plans for the future and working to make them a reality.	48.667	0.91548	15

of the well-being questionnaire items is ensured through the reliability established by Cronbach's Alpha. This hypothesis focuses on validating the reliability of the instrument used, ensuring that the questionnaire items are consistent with each other and provide reliable measures of the constructs intended to be assessed.

Reliability: Cronbach's alpha results for each scale

Given that the survey items are designed to measure similar constructs (e.g., overall well-being), we can calculate Cronbach's Alpha to assess the internal consistency of the items [25-29].

Cronbach's alpha value: An alpha of 0.580 indicates moderate to low reliability. Generally, an alpha value above 0.7 is considered acceptable in social research, although values between 0.6 and 0.7 may be permissible in the early stages of research. With 41 items, the scale is quite extensive. The means and standard deviations of the items vary, indicating different levels of agreement among participants (Table 1).

Table 1: Moderate to low reliability statistics.

Cronbach's alpha	Cronbach's alpha based on standardized items	Number of items
0.58	0.625	41

Interpretation for well-being index research: The scale exhibits moderate to low internal consistency. This could suggest that some items are not effectively measuring the same well-being construct in the group of older adult students. Cronbach's Alpha is a measure of internal consistency or reliability of a questionnaire. A Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.580, although moderately low, is not unusual in social sciences, especially in studies involving human attitudes and perceptions, which tend to be more subjective and variable (Tables 2 and 3).

The variability in the ages of the survey respondents could contribute to a lower Cronbach's Alpha (Table 4). Indeed, differences in life stages can significantly influence how people respond to questions about their well-being, relationships, and self-perceptions. Each age group may have different perspectives and experiences that impact their response to questionnaire questions.

7. Overall, I feel secure and positive about myself.	44.667	1.24595	15
8. I do not have many people who want to listen to me when I need to talk.	30.000	1.51186	15
9. I tend to worry about what other people think of me.	33.333	1.63299	15
10. I judge myself by what I believe is important, not by the values that others think are important.	48.667	1.59762	15
11. I have been able to build a home and a way of life to my liking.	46.000	1.18322	15
12. I am an active person in carrying out the projects I set for myself..	47.333	1.03280	15
13. If I had the chance, there are many things about myself that I would change.	38.667	1.64172	15
14. I feel that my friendships bring me many things.	46.667	1.39728	15
15. I tend to be influenced by people with strong convictions.	24.000	1.45406	15
16. Overall, I feel responsible for the situation in which I live.	49.333	1.38701	15
17. I feel good when I think about what I have done in the past and what I hope to do in the future.	46.000	1.24212	15
18. My goals in life have been more a source of satisfaction than frustration for me.	48.000	1.14642	15
19. I like most aspects of my personality.	43.333	0.61721	15
20. It seems to me that most people have more friends than I do.	25.333	1.72654	15
21. I am confident in my opinions even if they are contrary to the general consensus.	49.333	1.03280	15
22. The demands of daily life often depress me.	28.000	1.61245	15
23. I have a clear direction and purpose in my life.	46.000	0.82808	15
24. Overall, over time I feel that I am still learning more about myself.	52.000	0.56061	15
25. In many ways, I feel disappointed with my achievements in life.	26.000	1.35225	15
26. I have not experienced many close and trusting relationships.	23.333	1.58865	15
27. It is difficult for me to express my own opinions on controversial issues.	28.667	1.59762	15
28. I am quite good at handling many of my responsibilities in daily life.	47.333	0.45774	15
29. I am not clear about what I am trying to achieve in life.	22.667	1.09978	15
30. I stopped trying to make major improvements or changes in my life a long time ago.	30.667	1.48645	15
31. For the most part, I feel proud of who I am and the life I lead.	46.667	0.89974	15
32. I know I can trust my friends, and they know they can trust me.	48.667	1.30201	15
33. I often change my decisions if my friends or family disagree.	30.667	1.16292	15
34. I do not want to try new ways of doing things; my life is fine as it is.	32.000	1.47358	15
35. I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge what one thinks about oneself and the world.	50.000	1.06904	15
36. When I think about it, I really have not improved much as a person over the years.	26.667	1.54303	15
37. I feel that over time, I have developed significantly as a person.	53.333	0.48795	15
38. For me, life has been a continuous process of study, change, and growth.	52.667	0.59362	15
39. If I were unhappy with my life situation, I would take the most effective steps to change it.	46.667	1.29099	15

Table 3: Summary element statistics.

	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Maximum / Minimum	Variance	N of elements
Correlations between elements	0.039	-0.885	0.874	1.759	-0.988	0.137	41

Table 4: Frequency and percentage of age of students.

Age Range	Code	Frequency	%	% Cumulative
46-55	1	1	6.7	6.7
56-65	2	5	33.3	40.0
66-75	3	8	53.3	93.3
76-85	4	1	6.7	100.0
Total		15	100	

- 1. Changing perspectives with age:** Priorities, concerns, and values of an individual can change significantly throughout their life. For instance, younger individuals may be more focused on career development and relationships, while older individuals may reflect more on life satisfaction and deep personal connections.
- 2. Differences in life experiences:** Life experiences accumulated over time can alter one’s perception of oneself and relationships. Older individuals may have a more nuanced perspective or accept aspects of their lives that younger individuals are still exploring or challenging.
- 3. Changes in social relationship networks:** The quantity and quality of social relationships tend to change with age. Younger individuals may have broader but less profound social networks, while older individuals may have smaller but more intimate networks.

These differences may lead to greater variability in responses between age groups, potentially reducing the internal consistency of the questionnaire as measured by Cronbach’s Alpha. However, it’s essential to note that a moderately low Cronbach’s Alpha does not necessarily invalidate the study results, but it does suggest caution in interpreting the data and considering the possibility of variability due to factors such as age.

Assessment of age differences as an explanation for cronbach’s alpha

To assess whether age differences are significantly influencing the responses, we have conducted a more detailed analysis, namely the application of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to compare responses between different age groups (from 46 to 85 years).

ANOVA compares means between different groups (in this case, age groups) to see if there are statistically significant differences. Specifically:

Sum of squares between groups: Indicates variability due to differences between age groups.

Sum of squares within groups: Shows variability within each age group.

F and Significance (Sig.): The F value compares variability between groups with variability within groups. A high F value and a low Sig. value (usually less than 0.05) suggest that differences between age groups are statistically significant.

We will highlight some questionnaire items that show significant differences between age groups according to the ANOVA (Table 5):

- Item 2 (“I often feel lonely because I have few close friends to

share my concerns with”): Sig.=0.025, indicating a significant difference between age groups.

- Item 9 (“I tend to worry about what other people think of me”): Sig.=0.026, also suggesting significant age-related differences.
- Item 12 (“I am an active person in carrying out the projects I set for myself”): Sig.=0.011, indicating significant differences between age groups.
- Item 17 (“I feel good when I think about what I have done in the past and what I hope to do in the future”): Sig.=0.002, showing a significant difference.
- Item 22 (“The demands of daily life often get me down”): Sig.=0.012, indicating significant variability by age.
- Item 26 (“I have not experienced many close and trusting relationships”): Sig.=0.041, suggesting significant differences between age groups.
- Item 29 (“I’m not clear about what I’m trying to accomplish in life”): Sig.=0.014, indicating a significant difference between age groups.
- Item 34 (“I don’t want to try new ways of doing things; my life is fine as it is”): Sig.=0.027, showing significant differences.
- Item 34 (“I don’t want to try new ways of doing things; my life is fine as it is”): Sig.=0.027, showing significant differences.

The mentioned items above exhibit significant variations in responses based on the respondents’ age. This suggests that attitudes and perceptions related to these specific aspects vary among different age groups. These results can be valuable for better understanding how age influences people’s perceptions and experiences regarding aspects of their personal and social life.

To link the results of ANOVA by age with those items that, when removed, decrease or maintain Cronbach’s Alpha, we need to compare both sets of data (Table 6):

Items with significant differences in ANOVA by age: These are items that show significant variations in responses among different age groups. This suggests that the perception or experience related to these items varies depending on the respondents’ age.

Items affecting cronbach’s alpha: These are items that, when removed, result in a change in Cronbach’s Alpha. An increase in Alpha after removing an item indicates that this item was not aligned with the overall construct of the questionnaire, while a decrease or maintenance of Alpha suggests that the item is in line with the overall construct.

Table 5: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

		Sum of squares	gl	Mean square	F	Sig.
1. When I review the history of my life, I am content with how things have turned out.	Between groups	4.533	3	1.511	1.807	0.204
	Within groups	9.200	11	0.836		
	Total	13.733	14			
2. Often, I feel lonely because I have few close friends to share my concerns.	Between groups	20.633	3	6.878	4.641	0.025
	Within groups	16.300	11	1.482		
	Total	36.933	14			
3. I am not afraid to express my opinions, even when they are opposed to the opinions of most people.	Between groups	3.600	3	1.200	0.493	0.695
	Within groups	26.800	11	2.436		
	Total	30.400	14			
4. I worry about how other people evaluate the choices I have made in my life.	Between groups	2.633	3	0.878	0.760	0.539
	Within groups	12.700	11	1.155		
	Total	15.333	14			
5. It is difficult for me to direct my life toward a path that satisfies me.	Between groups	9.525	3	3.175	1.404	0.294
	Within groups	24.875	11	2.261		
	Total	34.400	14			
6. I enjoy making plans for the future and working to make them a reality.	Between groups	3.058	3	1.019	1.293	0.326
	Within groups	8.675	11	0.789		
	Total	11.733	14			
7. Overall, I feel confident and positive about myself.	Between groups	4.058	3	1.353	0.842	0.499
	Within groups	17.675	11	1.607		
	Total	21.733	14			
8. I don't have many people who want to listen to me when I need to talk.	Between groups	13.925	3	4.642	2.825	0.088
	Within groups	18.075	11	1.643		
	Total	32.000	14			
9. I tend to worry about what other people think of me.	Between groups	20.658	3	6.886	4.543	0.026
	Within groups	16.675	11	1.516		
	Total	37.333	14			
10. I judge myself by what I believe is important, not by the values others think are important.	Between groups	7.033	3	2.344	0.899	0.473
	Within groups	28.700	11	2.609		
	Total	35.733	14			
11. I have been able to build a home and a way of life to my liking.	Between groups	9.525	3	3.175	3.467	0.054
	Within groups	10.075	11	0.916		
	Total	19.600	14			
12. I am an active person in carrying out the projects I set for myself.	Between groups	9.258	3	3.086	5.982	0.011
	Within groups	5.675	11	0.516		
	Total	14.933	14			
13. If I had the chance, there are many things about myself that I would change.	Between groups	9.733	3	3.244	1.275	0.331
	Within groups	28.000	11	2.545		
	Total	37.733	14			
14. I feel that my friendships bring many things to me.	Between groups	5.033	3	1.678	0.828	0.506
	Within groups	22.300	11	2.027		
	Total	27.333	14			
15. I tend to be influenced by people with strong convictions.	Between groups	2.525	3	0.842	0.342	0.796
	Within groups	27.075	11	2.461		
	Total	29.600	14			

16. Overall, I feel responsible for the situation I live in.	Between groups	3.733	3	1.244	0.590	0.634
	Within groups	23.200	11	2.109		
	Total	26.933	14			
17. I feel good when I think about what I have done in the past and what I hope to do in the future.	Between groups	15.525	3	5.175	9.370	0.002
	Within groups	6.075	11	0.552		
	Total	21.600	14			
18. My goals in life have been more a source of satisfaction than frustration for me.	Between groups	4.900	3	1.633	1.331	.314
	Within groups	13.500	11	1.227		
	Total	18.400	14			
19. I like most aspects of my personality.	Between groups	.658	3	0.219	0.516	0.680
	Within groups	4.675	11	0.425		
	Total	5.333	14			
20. It seems to me that most people have more friends than I do.	Between groups	17.658	3	5.886	2.689	0.098
	Within groups	24.075	11	2.189		
	Total	41.733	14			
21. I have confidence in my opinions even if they are contrary to the general consensus.	Between groups	2.258	3	0.753	0.653	0.597
	Within groups	12.675	11	1.152		
	Total	14.933	14			
22. The demands of daily life often depress me.	Between groups	22.325	3	7.442	5.816	0.012
	Within groups	14.075	11	1.280		
	Total	36.400	14			
23. I have a clear direction and purpose in my life.	Between groups	2.525	3	0.842	1.309	0.321
	Within groups	7.075	11	0.643		
	Total	9.600	14			
24. Overall, over time, I feel I am still learning more about myself.	Between groups	1.600	3	0.533	2.095	0.159
	Within groups	2.800	11	0.255		
	Total	4.400	14			
25. In many ways, I feel disappointed with my achievements in life.	Between groups	6.925	3	2.308	1.360	0.306
	Within groups	18.675	11	1.698		
	Total	25.600	14			
26. I have not experienced many close and trusting relationships	Between groups	18.133	3	6.044	3.866	0.041
	Within groups	17.200	11	1.564		
	Total	35.333	14			
27. It is difficult for me to express my own opinions on controversial matters.	Between groups	4.933	3	1.644	0.587	0.636
	Within groups	30.800	11	2.800		
	Total	35.733	14			
28. I am quite good at handling many of my responsibilities in daily life.	Between groups	.233	3	0.078	0.317	0.813
	Within groups	2.700	11	0.245		
	Total	2.933	14			
29. I am not clear about what I am trying to achieve in life.	Between groups	10.258	3	3.419	5.635	0.014
	Within groups	6.675	11	0.607		
	Total	16.933	14			
30. I stopped trying to make major improvements or changes in my life a long time ago.	Between groups	11.733	3	3.911	2.241	0.141
	Within groups	19.200	11	1.745		
	Total	30.933	14			
31. For the most part, I am proud of who I am and the life I lead.	Between groups	2.533	3	0.844	1.056	0.407
	Within groups	8.800	11	0.800		
	Total	11.333	14			

32. I know I can trust my friends, and they know they can trust me.	Between groups	1.858	3	.619	0.311	0.817
	Within groups	21.875	11	1.989		
	Total	23.733	14			
33. I often change my decisions if my friends or family disagree.	Between groups	5.858	3	1.953	1.643	0.236
	Within groups	13.075	11	1.189		
	Total	18.933	14			
34. I don't want to try new ways of doing things; my life is fine as it is.	Between groups	16.725	3	5.575	4.484	0.027
	Within groups	13.675	11	1.243		
	Total	30.400	14			
35. I think it's important to have new experiences that challenge what one thinks about oneself and the world.	Between groups	9.700	3	3.233	5.646	0.014
	Within groups	6.300	11	0.573		
	Total	16.000	14			
36. When I think about it, over the years I haven't improved much as a person.	Between groups	5.258	3	1.753	0.687	0.579
	Within groups	28.075	11	2.552		
	Total	33.333	14			
37. I have the feeling that over time I have developed a lot as a person.	Between groups	0.633	3	0.211	0.860	0.490
	Within groups	2.700	11	0.245		
	Total	3.333	14			
38. For me, life has been a continuous process of study, change, and growth.	Between groups	2.258	3	0.753	3.096	0.072
	Within groups	2.675	11	0.243		
	Total	4.933	14			
39. If I were unhappy with my life situation, I would take the most effective steps to change it.	Between groups	9.033	3	3.011	2.316	0.132
	Within groups	14.300	11	1.300		
	Total	23.333	14			

Table 6: Element total statistics.

	Mean if item removed	Variance if item removed	Corrected total item correlation	Multiple correlation squared	Cronbach's alpha if item
Age	15.46000	1.43400	0.248	.	0.569
Gender	15.56000	1.49114	-0.085	.	0.584
1. When I review the history of my life, I am content with how things have turned out.	15.27333	1.41924	0.229	.	0.567
2. I often feel lonely because I have few close friends with whom to share my concerns.	15.41333	1.30981	0.395	.	0.542
3. I am not afraid to express my opinions, even when they are opposed to the opinions of the majority of people.	15.30000	1.42286	0.110	.	0.577
4. I am concerned about how other people evaluate the choices I have made in my life.	15.48667	1.54267	-0.271	.	0.605
5. I find it difficult to steer my life toward a path that satisfies me.	15.44000	1.34400	0.315	.	0.553
6. I enjoy making plans for the future and working to make them a reality.	15.23333	1.47524	-0.002	.	0.584
7. Overall, I feel secure and positive about myself.	15.27333	1.42924	0.129	.	0.575
8. I don't have many people who are willing to listen to me when I need to talk.	15.42000	1.41600	0.123	.	0.576
9. I tend to worry about what other people think of me.	15.38667	1.23552	0.609	.	0.513
10. I judge myself based on what I believe is important, not on the values that others think are important.	15.23333	1.51381	-0.143	.	0.606

11. I have been able to build a home and a lifestyle to my liking.	15.26000	1.42114	0.170	.	0.571
12. I am an active person when it comes to pursuing the projects I set for myself.	15.24667	1.47695	-0.018	.	0.586
13. If given the opportunity, there are many things about myself that I would change.	15.33333	1.30667	0.398	.	0.541
14. I feel that my friendships bring a lot to my life.	15.25333	1.45838	0.016	.	0.586
15. I tend to be influenced by people with strong convictions.	15.48000	1.44314	0.054	.	0.583
16. Overall, I feel responsible for the situation in which I live.	15.22667	1.43924	0.074	.	0.580
17. I feel good when I think about what I have done in the past and what I hope to do in the future.	15.26000	1.44971	0.060	.	0.581
18. My goals in life have been more a source of satisfaction than frustration for me.	15.24000	1.49400	-0.086	.	0.592
19. I like most aspects of my personality.	15.28667	1.44267	0.247	.	0.570
20. It seems to me that most people have more friends than I do.	15.46667	1.24810	0.532	.	0.521
21. I have confidence in my opinions even if they are contrary to the general consensus.	15.22667	1.46210	0.042	.	0.581
22. The demands of daily life often depress me.	15.44000	1.33971	0.315	.	0.552
23. I have a clear direction and goal in my life.	15.26000	1.44114	0.177	.	0.572
24. Overall, over time, I feel that I am still learning more about myself.	15.20000	1.44571	0.254	.	0.571
25. In many ways, I feel disappointed with my achievements in life.	15.46000	1.42543	0.122	.	0.575
26. I have not experienced many close and trusting relationships.	15.48667	1.36552	0.249	.	0.561
27. It is difficult for me to express my own opinions on controversial matters.	15.43333	1.43667	0.055	.	0.584
28. I am quite adept at handling many of my responsibilities in daily life.	15.24667	1.47410	0.063	.	0.579
29. I am not clear about what I am trying to achieve in life.	15.49333	1.42495	0.176	.	0.571
30. I stopped trying to make significant improvements or changes in my life a long time ago.	15.41333	1.49267	-0.087	.	0.598
31. For the most part, I feel proud of who I am and the life I lead.	15.25333	1.40838	0.312	.	0.562
32. I know I can trust my friends, and they know they can trust me.	15.23333	1.44524	0.067	.	0.581
33. I often change my decisions if my friends or family disagree.	15.41333	1.35838	0.410	.	0.549
34. I don't want to try new ways of doing things; my life is fine as it is.	15.40000	1.43714	0.069	.	0.581
35. I believe it is important to have new experiences that challenge what one thinks about oneself and the world.	15.22000	1.45600	0.061	.	0.580
36. When I think about it, over the years, I haven't improved much as a person.	15.45333	1.49124	-0.085	.	0.599
37. I have the feeling that over time, I have developed a lot as a person.	15.18667	1.44695	0.288	.	0.571
38. For me, life has been a continuous process of study, change, and growth.	15.19333	1.47924	0.003	.	0.581
39. If I felt unhappy with my life situation, I would take the most effective steps to change it.	15.25333	1.44267	0.077	.	0.580

Now, let's compare these two sets of data. So, first, we have Items with significant differences in ANOVA that affect Cronbach's Alpha:

Item 2 ("I often feel lonely..."): Significant ANOVA (Sig.=0.025), and according to the total item statistics, this item has a relatively high corrected item-total correlation of 0.395. Removing this item would decrease Cronbach's Alpha to 0.542, suggesting alignment with the overall construct of the questionnaire.

Item 9 ("I tend to worry about what other people think of me"): Significant ANOVA (Sig.=0.026), and it has a very high corrected item-total correlation of 0.609. Its removal would decrease Alpha to 0.513, indicating alignment with the overall construct.

Item 12 ("I am an active person in carrying out the projects..."): Significant ANOVA (Sig.=0.011), but there is no specific information about the effect of its removal on Cronbach's Alpha.

For items such as 2 and 9, where the removal of the item significantly decreases the Alpha, and there are significant variations in responses based on age, we can infer that these items are relevant to the overall construct of the questionnaire. However, their interpretation or importance may vary depending on age. This could suggest that aspects such as loneliness and concern for others' opinions have different levels of relevance or are experienced differently across different life stages.

RESULTS

The items have been examined in comparison to their opposing counterparts to identify the most significant contrasts. These antagonistic relationships illustrate how different aspects of attitudes and perceptions among older adults may be in conflict or not fully aligned with each other. These discrepancies, therefore, provide a more nuanced insight into their psychological and social well-being.

In each case, predominant proportions were analyzed, and inherent variability was explored. This process is crucial for gaining a deeper understanding of the psychological well-being of the studied sample. Based on the obtained results, relevant recommendations were formulated for the implementation of educational strategies, aiming to optimize the learning experience and promote psychological well-being in the classroom context.

Antagonistic relationship between personal pride (Item 31) and difficulty expressing opinions (Item 27)

On one hand, we will analyze responses to the statement in Item 31 ("For the most part, I feel proud of who I am and the life I lead"), using the Likert scale where 1 represents completely disagree and 6 completely agree.

A large majority of respondents (73.4%, combining categories 5 and 6) indicate feeling very or extremely proud of who they are and the life they lead. A smaller proportion (26.7%, combining categories 2 and 4) feels less proud, though still with a certain degree of pride (Table 7).

These results suggest that the majority of respondents have a positive perception of themselves and high satisfaction with their lives, which may reflect good self-esteem and a sense of accomplishment. Although most feel proud, there is variability

in the degree of pride, which could reflect differences in life experiences, achievements, and personal perception.

Table 7: Item 31. For the most part, I take pride in who I am and the life I lead.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	2.00	1	6.7	6.7
	4.00	3	20.0	26.7
	5.00	10	66.7	93.3
	6.00	1	6.7	100.0
	Total	15	100.0	100.0

Regarding the relevance to psychological well-being, feeling proud of oneself and the life one leads is important, as it is linked to self-acceptance and life satisfaction. A high degree of pride is often associated with a sense of self-efficacy and personal fulfilment. For those who feel less proud, it would be useful to explore strategies in their training to improve self-esteem and life satisfaction. Promoting the recognition of personal achievements and the development of a positive self-image can be beneficial in increasing a sense of pride and satisfaction.

On the other hand, we will analyze responses to the statement in Item 27 ("It is difficult for me to express my own opinions on controversial matters"). The majority of respondents (53.3%, combining categories 1 and 2) indicate not having much difficulty expressing their opinions on controversial topics. 33.3% of respondents (combining categories 4,5 and 6) moderately agree with the difficulty of expressing their opinions on controversial matters (Table 8).

Table 8: Item 27. It is difficult for me to express my own opinions on controversial matters.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	1.00	3	20.0	20.0
	2.00	5	33.3	53.3
	3.00	2	13.3	66.7
	4.00	2	13.3	80.0
	5.00	2	13.3	93.3
	6.00	1	6.7	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

A significant proportion of respondents feel comfortable expressing their opinions on controversial issues, which may indicate confidence in themselves and their beliefs. The expressed difficulty by other respondents may reflect challenges in confidence, communication, or fear of social repercussion.

Regarding the relevance to psychological well-being, the ability to express one's opinions is important for self-esteem and psychological well-being. For those who encounter difficulties, it may be useful to develop communication skills and confidence in their training.

The analysis of antagonistic relationships between "Personal pride" (Item 31) and "Difficulty expressing opinions" (Item 27) on the well-being scale effectively fulfills the objective of illustrating significant contrasts in the attitudes and perceptions of older

adults. This analysis reveals how different aspects of psychological and social well-being may be in conflict or not fully aligned. On one hand, we find that the majority of respondents feel proud of themselves and their lives, with a high percentage indicating feeling very or extremely proud. On the other hand, while a majority does not find it difficult to express their opinions on controversial topics, there is a considerable percentage that does experience some difficulty in this aspect.

This contrast between the high degree of personal pride and the difficulty expressing opinions reveals significant complexity in the experience of older adults. While personal pride reflects a positive self-image and satisfaction with life, the difficulty expressing opinions may indicate a discrepancy between this positive self-image and the confidence to engage in social or controversial discussions. This suggests that, although individuals may feel satisfied and positive about themselves and their achievements, they may face challenges when communicating their ideas and opinions in social contexts, especially on controversial topics.

Given this analysis, it is recommended to develop training programs for older adults that strengthen their communication and opinion expression skills, thus promoting greater alignment between their self-esteem and their ability to express themselves in public. This may include workshops on assertive communication and handling debate situations, supporting older adults not only in feeling proud of who they are but also in feeling confident and capable of expressing their opinions effectively. These strategies could enhance their learning experience and contribute significantly to their overall well-being.

Confidence in own opinions (Item 21) vs. Susceptibility to others’ convictions (Item 15)

On one hand, we will analyze responses to the statement in Item 21 (“I have confidence in my opinions even if they are contrary to general consensus”). A significant majority of respondents (73.3%, combining categories 5 and 6) show high or very high confidence in their opinions, even if they are contrary to general consensus. 26.6% (combining categories 3 and 4) indicate moderate or fairly high confidence to not having that confidence (Table 9).

Table 9: Item 21. I have confidence in my opinions even if they are contrary to the general consensus.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
	3.00	2	13.3	13.3
	4.00	2	13.3	26.7
Valid	5.00	6	40.0	66.7
	6.00	5	33.3	100.0
	Total	15	100.0	100.0

These results suggest that the majority of respondents have confidence in their own opinions and are willing to maintain them even in the face of contrary opinions or group pressures. Regarding the relevance to psychological well-being, maintaining confidence in one’s opinions is an important aspect, also for self-affirmation, as it reflects a person’s ability to maintain individuality and autonomy. It is important to balance confidence in one’s opinions with openness to new ideas and the ability to

consider alternative perspectives.

For those with a lower level of confidence, strategies to strengthen self-confidence and self-affirmation could be explored in training. It would be beneficial to promote the development of healthy self-esteem and critical thinking skills while encouraging openness and flexibility in thinking.

On the other hand, we will analyze responses to the statement in Item 15 (“I tend to be influenced by people with strong convictions”). A significant majority of respondents (66.6%, combining categories 1 and 2) indicate not being strongly influenced by individuals with strong convictions. 26.6% of respondents (combining categories 4 and 5) show some degree of agreement with being influenced by people with strong convictions (Table 10).

Table 10: Item 15. I tend to be influenced by people with strong convictions.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
	1.00	5	33.3	33.3
	2.00	5	33.3	66.7
Valid	3.00	1	6.7	73.3
	4.00	2	13.3	86.7
	5.00	2	13.3	100.0
	Total	15	100.0	100.0

These results suggest that the majority of respondents tend to maintain their own opinions and beliefs, even in the face of individuals with strong convictions. Regarding the relevance to Psychological Well-being, the ability to maintain autonomy in one’s beliefs and opinions is important for psychological well-being, as it reflects self-affirmation and individuality. It is important to balance openness to new ideas with the ability to maintain autonomy in one’s beliefs and decisions.

For those who feel more influenced, it could be useful to work on strengthening self-affirmation and confidence in their own beliefs in training. Promoting the development of critical thinking skills and self-confidence can be beneficial for those seeking to increase their autonomy in the face of external influences.

The analysis of antagonistic relationships between “Confidence in own opinions” (Item 21) and “Susceptibility to others’ convictions” (Item 15) on the well-being scale serves the purpose of identifying significant contrasts in the attitudes and perceptions of older adults. This analysis demonstrates how different aspects of psychological well-being may be in conflict or not fully aligned, providing a nuanced insight into the studied sample.

In the case of Item 21, we observe that a significant majority of respondents exhibit high confidence in their own opinions, even if these opinions are contrary to the general consensus. This reflects strong self-affirmation and confidence in their personal beliefs. In contrast, the results of Item 15 reveal that a majority also indicates not being strongly influenced by individuals with strong convictions, suggesting a tendency towards autonomy in opinions and beliefs, even in the face of strong external influences.

This antagonism between confidence in one’s own opinions

and resistance to being influenced by the convictions of others highlights a complexity in the dynamics of self-affirmation and social influence. On one hand, confidence in one’s own opinions can be seen as a sign of strength and self-assurance. On the other hand, lower susceptibility to being influenced by others suggests independence in thinking and an ability to stand firm against social pressures or external convictions.

These findings are crucial for gaining a deeper understanding of the psychological well-being of the studied sample and provide a foundation for the implementation of educational strategies. The development of critical thinking skills and self-confidence can be encouraged, while also promoting openness and flexibility in thinking. For those with lower confidence or higher susceptibility, it would be beneficial to explore strategies to strengthen their self-affirmation and self-expression skills. These recommendations can help optimize the learning experience and promote psychological well-being in the classroom context, considering the variability in responses and the inherent subjectivity in the perception of these attitudes.

Satisfaction with personal achievements (Item 25) vs. Disappointment with personal achievements (Item 25)

We will analyze responses to the statement in Item 25 (“In many ways, I feel disappointed with my achievements in life”). A majority of respondents (66.6%, combining categories 1 and 2) do not feel disappointed with their achievements in life. 20.0% of respondents (category 5) agree with feeling disappointed with their achievements (Table 11).

Table 11: Item 25. In many aspects, I feel disappointed with my achievements in life.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	1.00	2	13.3	13.3
	2.00	8	53.3	66.7
	3.00	2	13.3	80.0
	5.00	3	20.0	100.0
	Total	15	100.0	100.0

These results suggest that the majority of respondents are generally satisfied with their achievements in life, although there is a significant proportion that feels some level of disappointment. Regarding the relevance to psychological well-being, satisfaction or disappointment with personal achievements has a significant impact, also on self-esteem.

For those who feel disappointment, it may be useful in training to reassess and adjust their goals and expectations to better align them with their values and current circumstances. It is important to address the concerns of those who feel significant disappointment, possibly through counselling or support for goal reassessment. Encouraging a realistic and healthy perspective on personal achievements and providing support for expectation management and goal redefinition can be beneficial.

The analysis of antagonistic relationships between “Satisfaction with personal achievements” and “Disappointment with personal achievements” within the same item (Item 25) on the well-being scale provides a detailed insight into how different aspects of attitudes and perceptions among older adults may not align

completely. This approach, comparing predominant proportions and exploring inherent variability, is crucial for gaining a deep understanding of the psychological well-being of the studied sample.

In this item, it is observed that a majority of respondents do not feel disappointed with their achievements in life, indicating a general tendency toward personal satisfaction and a sense of accomplishment. However, there is a significant proportion of respondents who do experience disappointment regarding their achievements, suggesting diversity in the perception of personal achievements and levels of aspiration among participants. This contrast reflects differences in how individuals perceive and value their achievements and successes in life, directly impacting their self-esteem and personal satisfaction.

The ability to generalize these results is limited due to the sample size and the perception of achievements and related disappointment is highly subjective, possibly influenced by personal and contextual factors. In terms of relevance to psychological well-being, satisfaction or disappointment with personal achievements has a significant impact, and for those who feel disappointment, it may be helpful to reassess and adjust their goals and expectations to better align them with their values and current circumstances.

In conclusion, the predominance of satisfaction over disappointment in personal achievements suggests a generally positive trend. However, addressing the concerns of those who experience disappointment is important, possibly through counselling or support for goal reassessment. Encouraging a realistic and healthy perspective on personal achievements and providing support for expectation management and goal redefinition can be beneficial. This analysis, along with other survey responses, provides a more comprehensive understanding of how respondents perceive their achievements and their overall life satisfaction.

Perception of personal responsibility (Item 16) vs. Disappointment with personal achievements (Item 25)

On one hand, we will analyze responses to the statement in Item 16 (“In general, I feel that I am responsible for the situation I am in”). A significant majority of respondents (80.0%, combining categories 5 and 6) feel very or extremely responsible for the situation they are in. 20.1% of respondents (combining categories 1, 3, and 4) show a lower degree of agreement with feeling responsible for their situation (Table 12).

Table 12: Item 16. Overall, I feel responsible for the situation in which I live.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	1.00	1	6.7	6.7
	3.00	1	6.7	13.3
	4.00	1	6.7	20.0
	5.00	6	40.0	60.0
	6.00	6	40.0	100.0
	Total	15	100.0	100.0

These results suggest that the majority of respondents feel a high

degree of personal control and responsibility for their current situation, reflecting a strong sense of self-efficacy. Regarding the relevance to psychological well-being, feeling responsible for one’s own situation is crucial, as it is associated with personal agency and the ability to make positive changes. A strong sense of personal responsibility is related to proactivity and the ability to adapt and manage challenges.

For those who feel less responsibility, it would be beneficial to promote, during training, the development of personal agency and skills to manage their environment. Encouraging self-efficacy, conscious decision-making, and adaptation strategies can be beneficial for those seeking to increase their sense of responsibility over their situation.

On the other hand, we will return to the statement in Item 25 (“In many ways, I feel disappointed with my achievements in life”). As we have seen earlier, a majority of respondents (66.6%, combining categories 1 and 2) do not feel disappointed with their achievements in life. 20.0% of respondents (category 5) agree with feeling disappointed by their achievements (Table 11). These results suggest that the majority of respondents are generally satisfied with their achievements in life, although there is a significant proportion that feels some level of disappointment.

The analysis of antagonistic relationships between “Perception of personal responsibility” (Item 16) and “Disappointment with personal achievements” (Item 25) on the well-being scale reveals how different aspects of attitudes and perceptions among older adults may be in conflict or not fully aligned. This analysis is crucial for understanding in-depth the psychological well-being of the studied sample and provides a nuanced insight into their emotional and social state.

On one hand, the “Perception of personal responsibility” shows that a significant majority of respondents feel very or extremely responsible for the situation they are in. This suggests a high degree of personal control and responsibility for their current situation, reflecting a strong sense of self-efficacy. On the other hand, in Item 25, we find that, while the majority of respondents do not feel disappointed with their achievements in life, there is a significant segment that does experience disappointment.

This contrast between the sense of personal responsibility and disappointment with personal achievements illustrates how the perception of control and responsibility over one’s life may be in tension with feelings of disappointment or dissatisfaction with personal achievements. While the perception of personal responsibility implies a proactive and controlling attitude, disappointment with personal achievements may indicate a gap between expectations and lived reality, impacting self-esteem and personal satisfaction.

The ability to generalize these results is limited due to the sample size, and perceptions of both responsibility and achievements are highly subjective, influenced by personal and contextual factors. In terms of psychological well-being, feeling responsible for one’s own situation is crucial, as it is associated with personal agency and the ability to make positive changes. However, disappointment with personal achievements requires attention, as it may be necessary to reassess and adjust goals and expectations.

In conclusion, the prevalence of the sense of personal responsibility suggests a generally proactive attitude, but it is important to address the concerns of those experiencing disappointment. Encouraging a realistic and healthy perspective on personal achievements and providing support for expectation management and goal redefinition can be beneficial. This analysis, along with other survey responses, provides a more comprehensive understanding of how respondents perceive their control, responsibility, and satisfaction with their lives.

Proactivity in personal projects (Item 12) vs. Ceasing to try improvements or changes (Item 30)

On one hand, we will analyze responses to the statement in Item 12 (“I am an active person in carrying out the projects I have set for myself”). A significant majority of respondents (80.0%, combining categories 5 and 6) feel very or extremely active in carrying out their personal projects. 20.1% of respondents (combining categories 2,3 and 4) show a lower degree of agreement with being active in the realization of their projects (Table 13).

Table 13: Item 12. I am an active person when it comes to pursuing the projects I set for myself.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
	2.00	1	6.7	6.7
	3.00	1	6.7	13.3
	4.00	1	6.7	20.0
Valid	5.00	10	66.7	86.7
	6.00	2	13.3	100.0
	Total	15	100.0	100.0

These results suggest that the majority of respondents have a high degree of commitment and proactivity in the realization of their personal projects, indicating a strong orientation toward achievement and self-efficacy. Regarding the relevance to psychological well-being, being active in the realization of personal projects is important, as it contributes to the sense of purpose and achievement. A proactive attitude towards personal projects is associated with higher self-efficacy and personal satisfaction.

For those with a lower degree of activity, it would be helpful to explore, in training, strategies to increase motivation and enhance project management skills. Encouraging planning, goal-setting, and time management techniques can be beneficial for those seeking to be more active in their personal projects.

On the other hand, we will analyze responses to the statement in Item 30 (“I stopped trying to make significant improvements or changes in my life a long time ago”). A majority of respondents (46.6%, combining categories 1 and 2) disagree with the idea that they have stopped trying to make significant improvements or changes in their lives. 40% of respondents (combining categories 4 and 5) somewhat agree that they have stopped trying to make significant improvements or changes (Table 14).

Table 14: Item 30. I stopped trying to make significant improvements or

changes in my life a long time ago.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	1.00	2	13.3	13.3
	2.00	5	33.3	46.7
	3.00	2	13.3	60.0
	4.00	2	13.3	73.3
	5.00	4	26.7	100.0
	Total	15	100.0	100.0

These results suggest that the majority of respondents feel they have continued to try to improve and change to varying degrees over the years.

In terms of relevance to psychological well-being, the perception of personal improvement and growth is important, as it contributes to self-esteem and life satisfaction. For those who feel they have stopped making efforts to improve, identifying areas for improvement and setting clear goals can be beneficial.

For those who feel they have stopped improving, it would be helpful to focus, in training, on personal development and motivation strategies. Encouraging personal reflection, goal-setting, and continuous learning can help improve the perception of one’s personal growth.

The analysis of antagonistic relationships between “Proactivity in personal projects” (Item 12) and “Ceasing to try improvements or changes” (Item 30) on the well-being scale offers an interesting perspective on the attitudes and perceptions of older adults. These antagonistic relationships provide a more nuanced view of their psychological and social well-being, highlighting how different aspects may be in conflict or not fully aligned.

On one hand, “Proactivity in personal projects” shows that a significant majority of respondents feel very or extremely active in carrying out their personal projects. This indicates a high level of commitment and a strong orientation toward achievement, reflecting a proactive attitude and good self-efficacy. On the other hand, “Ceasing to try improvements or changes” reveals that a notable group of respondents agrees to having stopped trying to make significant improvements or changes in their lives. This could indicate a more passive attitude or a conformity with the status.

This contrast between proactivity in personal projects and ceasing to try improvements or changes illustrates how an active and dynamic attitude towards personal goals can coexist with a sense of resignation or conformity in other areas of life. While proactivity reflects an active approach to achieving goals, ceasing to try improvements may be an indicator of discouragement, lack of motivation, or a perception of insurmountable limitations.

The ability to generalize these results is limited due to the sample size, and perceptions of proactivity and ceasing efforts are highly subjective and may be influenced by personal and contextual factors. In terms of psychological well-being, being proactive in personal projects is crucial to maintaining a sense of purpose and achievement, while the perception of having stopped

trying improvements may require attention to foster continuous personal development and motivation.

In conclusion, the prevalence of proactivity in personal projects suggests an active commitment to personal achievement, but it is important to address the concerns of those who have stopped trying improvements. Encouraging personal reflection, goal-setting, and continuous learning can be beneficial for those seeking to reignite their drive for personal development. This analysis, along with other survey responses, provides a more comprehensive understanding of how respondents approach their personal goals and their attitude towards change and improvement in their lives.

High self-awareness and personal growth (Item 24) vs. Resistance to personal change (Item 13)

On one hand, we will analyze the responses to the statement in Item 24 (“In general, over time, I feel that I continue learning more about myself”). An overwhelming majority of the respondents (93.4% summing categories 5 and 6) strongly or extremely agree with the idea that they continue learning more about themselves as time passes. Only a small proportion (6.7%, category 4) agrees to some extent, still indicating a positive trend towards self-learning (Table 15).

Table 15: Item 24. Overall, over time, I feel that I am still learning more about myself.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	4.00	1	6.7	6.7
	5.00	10	66.7	73.3
	6.00	4	26.7	100.0
	Total	15	100.0	100.0

These results suggest that most respondents experience a high degree of self-awareness and continuous personal growth.

Regarding the relevance to psychological well-being, continuous self-learning and self-awareness are crucial as they facilitate a deeper understanding of oneself and better adaptation to life situations. Continuous self-learning is related to personal development and the ability to cope with and adapt to changes and challenges in life.

For those with a lower degree of self-learning, it could be beneficial in training to explore ways to foster introspection and self-awareness. Promoting practices that increase self-awareness, such as meditation, reflection, and journaling, may be beneficial for ongoing personal development.

On the other hand, we will analyze the responses to the statement in Item 13 (“If given the chance, there are many things about myself I would change”). A majority of the respondents (73.3% summing categories 4,5 and 6) express some degree of agreement with the idea of wanting to change many things about themselves. 26.6% of the respondents (Summing categories 1 and 2) indicate little or no desire to change many things about themselves (Table 16). These results suggest that a significant proportion of respondents are reflecting on themselves and have a desire for

personal changes.

Table 16: Item 13. If given the opportunity, there are many things about myself that I would change.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	1.00	2	13.3	13.3
	2.00	2	13.3	26.7
	4.00	5	33.3	60.0
	5.00	4	26.7	86.7
	6.00	2	13.3	100.0
	Total	15	100.0	100.0

Regarding the relevance to psychological well-being, the desire to change and improve aspects of oneself can be an indicator of a proactive attitude toward personal development and growth. It is important to balance the desire for change with self-acceptance, promoting a healthy approach to personal growth.

For those expressing a strong desire for change, it could be beneficial in training to explore specific areas for development and establish realistic growth goals. Encouraging self-exploration, self-acceptance, and identifying areas for personal growth can be beneficial for those seeking personal change.

The analysis of antagonistic relationships between “High self-awareness and personal growth” (Item 24) and “Resistance to personal change” (Item 13) on the well-being scale reflects interesting aspects of attitudes and perceptions among older adults. This comparison illustrates how different aspects of self-assessment and personal development can coexist or conflict, providing a nuanced insight into their psychological and social well-being.

On one hand, Item 24, associated with high self-awareness and personal growth, reveals that an overwhelming majority of respondents strongly or extremely agree with continuing to learn more about themselves over time. This suggests a high level of self-awareness and ongoing commitment to self-learning and self-exploration. This approach to continuous personal growth is indicative of a proactive attitude and strong self-efficacy.

However, Item 13, addressing resistance to personal change, shows that a majority of respondents express some degree of agreement with wanting to change many things about themselves. This could be interpreted as a sign of dissatisfaction with certain personal aspects or an openness to change and improvement.

The antagonistic relationship between these two items highlights how the willingness for personal growth and self-knowledge can coexist with the desire or perception of the need for significant personal changes. This reflects different levels of personal satisfaction and openness to change. While some individuals may feel content and on a continuous path of self-discovery, others may experience a greater need for change and personal development.

In terms of psychological well-being, continuous self-learning and self-awareness are fundamental as they facilitate a deeper

understanding of oneself and better adaptation to life situations. Simultaneously, the desire to change aspects of oneself can be an indicator of a proactive attitude toward personal development and growth. It is important to balance the desire for change with self-acceptance, fostering a healthy approach to personal growth.

Ultimately, the trend towards continuous self-learning and exploration, coupled with the interest in changing and improving oneself, suggests dynamism in how respondents approach their personal development. For those with a strong desire for change, exploring specific areas for development and setting realistic growth goals could be beneficial. Promoting self-exploration, self-acceptance, and the identification of areas for personal growth can be advantageous for those seeking personal change. These results, analyzed in conjunction with other survey responses, provide a comprehensive insight into how respondents perceive their personal development and readiness for change over time.

Well-being in reflecting on the past and future (Item 17) vs. Handling daily responsibilities (Item 28)

On one hand, we will analyze responses to the statement in Item 17 (“I feel good when I think about what I have done in the past and what I expect to do in the future”). A significant majority of respondents (73.3% combining categories 5 and 6) feel very or extremely good when thinking about what they have accomplished in the past and what they hope to do in the future. A 20.0% of respondents (Combining categories 1, 3, and 4) exhibit a lower level of well-being when reflecting on their past and future (Table 17).

Table 17: Item 17. I feel good when I think about what I have done in the past and what I hope to do in the future.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	1.00	1	6.7	6.7
	3.00	1	6.7	13.3
	4.00	2	13.3	26.7
	5.00	9	60.0	86.7
	6.00	2	13.3	100.0
	Total	15	100.0	100.0

These results suggest that most respondents have a positive perception of their past achievements and feel optimistic about their plans and future goals. In terms of relevance to psychological well-being, feeling good when reflecting on the past and having positive expectations for the future is crucial, as it contributes to a sense of continuity and purpose in life. A positive perception of the past and the future is associated with increased self-efficacy and a sense of hope and optimism.

For those with a less positive perception, exploring strategies to improve satisfaction with the past and optimism towards the future in training could be helpful. Encouraging positive reflection, recognizing past achievements, and planning future goals can be beneficial for overall well-being.

On the other hand, we will analyze responses to the statement in Item 28 (“I am quite good at handling many of my responsibilities

in daily life”). 73.3% of respondents feel that they have a very good ability to manage their responsibilities, indicating a high level of competence in handling their daily tasks (Table 18).

Table 18: Item 28. I am quite adept at handling many of my responsibilities in daily life.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
	4.00	4	26.7	26.7
Valid	5.00	11	73.3	100.0
	Total	15	100.0	100.0

These results suggest that the majority of respondents feel competent in handling their daily responsibilities, which may reflect effective organizational skills and proficient time management. Regarding its relevance to Psychological Well-being, the ability to effectively manage daily responsibilities is crucial, as it contributes to the sense of control and competence. Feeling competent in handling daily responsibilities is associated with increased self-efficacy and emotional stability. Promoting strategies that enhance efficiency and responsibility management can be beneficial in training, even for those who already perceive themselves as competent.

The analysis of the antagonistic relationships between “Well-being reflecting on the past and future” (Item 17) and “Management of daily responsibilities” (Item 28) on the well-being scale reveals an interesting dynamic in respondents’ perceptions and attitudes. These items, though different in their focus, provide a comprehensive insight into individuals’ psychological and practical well-being.

On one hand, Item 17 focuses on emotional perception and life continuity, where the majority of respondents express satisfaction and optimism when reflecting on their past and future. A significant majority feels very or extremely well when thinking about what they have accomplished in the past and what they hope to do in the future. This indicates a sense of satisfaction with the past and optimism toward the future, contributing to a feeling of continuity and purpose in life. A positive perception of the past and future is also associated with increased self-efficacy and a sense of hope and optimism.

Conversely, Item 28 addresses efficiency and practical competence in day-to-day activities. All respondents indicate having a quite good or very good ability to handle their daily responsibilities, reflecting effective organizational skills and good time management. This high competence in managing daily responsibilities contributes to the sense of control and competence, crucial for psychological well-being.

The antagonistic relationship between these two items highlights how emotional satisfaction and the perception of continuity in life can coexist with high practical competence in handling daily responsibilities. While Item 17 reflects more introspective and emotional aspects of well-being, Item 28 focuses on more practical and everyday aspects. This combination of emotional satisfaction and practical competence suggests a balanced approach to well-being, encompassing both mental health and effectiveness in

daily tasks.

In terms of psychological well-being, both aspects are crucial. Feeling good about one’s past and future enhances emotional quality of life, while being competent in managing daily responsibilities provides a sense of efficacy and control. For those with a less positive perception of the past and future, it would be useful to explore strategies to improve satisfaction with the past and optimism toward the future. At the same time, promoting strategies to enhance efficiency and responsibility management can be beneficial for everyone, even those who already feel competent.

In conclusion, the combination of a positive perception of the past and future with high competence in managing daily responsibilities provides a holistic perspective on the well-being of the respondents. These results, along with other survey responses, offer a comprehensive insight into how respondents navigate both their emotions and daily responsibilities, contributing to their overall well-being.

Satisfaction with life goals (Item 18) vs. Appreciation of personality (Item 19)

On one hand, we will analyze the responses to the statement of item 18 (“My goals in life have been more a source of satisfaction than frustration for me”). A significant majority of respondents (73.4%, combining categories 5 and 6) express high or very high satisfaction with their life goals, considering them more a source of satisfaction than frustration. Twenty percent of respondents (Combining categories 2 and 3) indicate a lower level of satisfaction regarding their life goals (Table 19). These results suggest that most respondents find satisfaction in their life goals, which may indicate clear and achievable goals or a good ability to manage expectations and outcomes.

Table 19: Item 18. My goals in life have been more a source of satisfaction than frustration for me.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
	2.00	1	6.7	6.7
	3.00	1	6.7	13.3
Valid	4.00	2	13.3	26.7
	5.00	7	46.7	73.3
	6.00	4	26.7	100.0
	Total	15	100.0	100.0

In terms of relevance to psychological well-being, having goals that are a source of satisfaction rather than frustration is important, as it contributes to a sense of purpose and achievement. A positive perception of one’s goals is related to higher self-efficacy and motivation for personal and professional development.

For those who experience less satisfaction with their goals, it might be useful, in training, to review and adjust their goals to make them more realistic and achievable. Promoting self-evaluation, realistic goal-setting, and effective strategies for managing expectations can be beneficial in increasing satisfaction

with life goals.

On the other hand, we will analyze the responses to the statement of item 19 (“I like most aspects of my personality”).

An overwhelming majority of respondents (93.3%, combining categories 4 and 5) express being quite or very much in agreement with liking most aspects of their personality. Only a small proportion (6.7%, category 3) is moderately in agreement (Table 20). These results suggest that most respondents have a positive perception of their personality and show signs of good self-esteem and self-acceptance.

Table 20: Item 19. I like most aspects of my personality.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	3.00	1	6.7	6.7
	4.00	8	53.3	60.0
	5.00	6	40.0	100.0
	Total	15	100.0	100.0

In terms of relevance to psychological well-being, the ability to appreciate one’s own personality is important, also for mental health, as it reflects self-acceptance and a positive self-image. Feeling good about one’s personality is related to higher self-efficacy and motivation for personal development.

For those with a more moderate appreciation of their personality, it might be useful, in training, to explore strategies to improve self-acceptance and self-esteem. Encouraging self-exploration and developing a positive self-image can be beneficial in strengthening personal appreciation.

The analysis of the antagonistic relationships between “Satisfaction with life goals” (Item 18) and “Appreciation of personality” (Item 19) on the well-being scale reveals significant aspects of the psychological and social well-being of the respondents. These items, although addressing different dimensions of self-concept and personal satisfaction, contribute collectively to a deeper understanding of individuals’ self-esteem and personal fulfilment.

Item 18 focuses on the achievement of goals and aspirations. The majority of respondents are satisfied with their life goals, indicating that these are more a source of satisfaction than frustration. This suggests that respondents have clear and achievable goals and are capable of managing their expectations and outcomes effectively. Satisfaction with life goals is crucial for psychological well-being, as it contributes to a sense of purpose and accomplishment. It is also related to higher self-efficacy and motivation for personal and professional development.

On the other hand, Item 19 reflects self-acceptance and self-esteem. A large proportion of respondents have a positive perception of their personality, showing signs of good self-esteem and self-acceptance. High self-esteem and personal appreciation indicate that the majority feel positively about their personality, although there is variability in the degree of affinity. The ability to appreciate one’s own personality is important for psychological well-being and mental health, reflecting self-acceptance and a

positive self-image.

The contrast between these two items illustrates how personal goal achievement and satisfaction can coexist with a positive perception of one’s personality. While Item 18 focuses on more external and goal-oriented aspects of self-concept, Item 19 addresses the internal and emotional dimension of self-concept. This combination suggests that respondents not only strive to achieve external goals but also maintain a positive attitude toward themselves, which is essential for comprehensive mental health.

In conclusion, the antagonistic relationship between satisfaction with life goals and appreciation of personality reveals a balanced picture of the psychological well-being of the respondents. Satisfaction with personal achievements and a positive perception of one’s personality combine to form a solid foundation for self-esteem and personal fulfilment. These results, along with other survey responses, provide a comprehensive understanding of how respondents perceive and value both their achievements and personal identity, contributing to their overall well-being.

Daily demands management (Item 22) vs. Clarity of direction and goals (Item 23)

On one hand, we will analyze the responses to the statement of Item 22 (“The demands of daily life often depress me”).

A majority of respondents (60%, combining categories 1 and 2) do not feel depressed or negatively affected by the demands of daily life. 33.3% of respondents (Combining categories 4,5 and 6) indicate feeling moderately or strongly affected by depression due to daily demands (Table 21).

Table 21: Item 22. The demands of daily life often depress me.

	Frequency	Percentage P	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	1.00	3	20.0	20.0
	2.00	6	40.0	60.0
	3.00	1	6.7	66.7
	4.00	2	13.3	80.0
	5.00	2	13.3	93.3
	6.00	1	6.7	100.0
	Total	15	100.0	100.0

These results suggest that the majority of respondents can handle the demands of daily life without feeling depressed.

Regarding the relevance to psychological well-being, how individuals perceive and manage daily demands is crucial for mental well-being as well. Identifying effective strategies for handling stress and demands can be crucial for those who feel more affected.

It is important to pay attention to those indicating a higher tendency towards depression due to daily demands. Promoting psychological well-being through effective coping strategies, social support, and, if necessary, professional counselling, can be beneficial for those more affected.

On the other hand, we will analyze the responses to the statement

of Item 23 (“I have a clear direction and purpose in my life”).

A significant majority of respondents (93.3%, combining categories 4,5 and 6) feel that they have a quiet, very, or extremely clear direction and goals in life. Only a small proportion (6.7%, category 3) indicates having only moderate clarity in their direction and life goals (Table 22).

Table 22: Item 23. I have a clear direction and goal in my life.

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
	3.00	1	6.7	6.7
	4.00	6	40.0	46.7
Valid	5.00	6	40.0	86.7
	6.00	2	13.3	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

These results suggest that most respondents have a clear sense of direction and purpose in their lives, which may indicate conscious life planning and well-defined goals.

Regarding the relevance to psychological well-being, having clear direction and goals in life is crucial as it provides a sense of purpose and motivation. Clear life direction and goals are associated with better life planning and an increased sense of self-efficacy. For those with less clarity, it may be beneficial to explore, in training, ways to develop greater direction and goal definition. Promoting self-exploration, goal-setting, and life planning can be advantageous in enhancing clarity in life direction and goals.

The analysis of antagonistic relationships between “Handling daily demands” (Item 22) and “Clarity of direction and goals” (Item 23) on the well-being scale offers a comprehensive perspective on the balance between managing daily responsibilities and long-term vision in the lives of respondents.

On one hand, Item 22 addresses how individuals cope with daily pressures and demands. A majority of respondents (60%) do not feel depressed by daily demands, indicating good stress management and coping abilities. Effectively handling daily tasks is essential for maintaining stable psychological and mental well-being. The ability to manage these demands without significant emotional impact is an indicator of resilience and effective coping strategies.

On the other hand, Item 23 focuses on long-term vision and life goals. A significant majority (93.3% summing up categories 4,5 and 6) of respondents has clarity in their life direction and goals. This clarity in direction and goals is crucial for psychological well-being as it provides a sense of purpose, motivation, and an increased sense of self-efficacy. Having well-defined goals and a clear sense of where one is headed in life can positively influence decision-making and future planning.

The contrast between these two items reveals how individuals can effectively handle daily responsibilities while maintaining a clear vision of their long-term goals. This combination of practical skills in daily life and a long-term life orientation is indicative of a balanced and holistic approach to psychological well-being.

It is important to recognize and encourage the ability of older

adults to balance effective management of daily demands with a clear vision of their long-term goals and life plans. Promoting effective coping strategies for daily demands while also encouraging clarity in life planning and goals can enhance the psychological well-being of this population.

In the educational and community context, it is beneficial to implement programs that assist older adults in balancing their daily tasks with the pursuit of their long-term goals, thereby offering a more enriching learning experience and promoting their overall well-being.

This comparison provides a more comprehensive insight into how respondents perceive and manage both their daily responsibilities and their aspirations and long-term life plans, emphasizing the importance of a holistic approach to the psychological and social well-being of older individuals.

These opposing pairs illustrate how different aspects of life and self-perception can interact and provide a nuanced view of the psychological and social well-being of older individuals. Comparing these items can help better understand the complexities of their experiences and contribute to the development of educational strategies that promote their well-being.

DISCUSSION

The discussion of the study on the well-being of older adults at the Permanent University for Adults in Alicante is deepened by contrasting the obtained results with previous research, providing a more comprehensive perspective on how these findings align or differ from current trends in scientific literature. This comparison is crucial to contextualize the research within the broader field of well-being in old age.

Starting with a summary of the main findings, the study highlights the interrelation between various psychological aspects such as personal pride, the ability to express opinions, satisfaction with personal achievements, and self-awareness in older adults. These elements reflect a complex interplay of factors contributing to overall well-being. The research by Wright, et al., and Fernández, et al., for example, emphasizes the importance of self-esteem and satisfaction with personal achievements, aspects that this study corroborates and extends to the context of adult education, including the online teaching environment [30-32].

Regarding the generalizability of the results, it is important to consider that, although the findings are relevant to the participants in this particular study, they may not be directly applicable to other contexts or cultures. This limitation opens opportunities for future research that could explore whether these results are consistent in different educational settings or demographic groups [33].

The practical relevance of the results is highlighted in their potential application in pedagogical strategies and clinical practices. Educators and healthcare professionals could use these findings to develop interventions and programs aimed at improving the psychological well-being of older adults, taking into account the various identified factors [19,33,34].

A reflection on the strengths and limitations of the study is crucial. While the detailed focus and the wide range of variables

studied are strengths, limitations such as sample size and potential response bias in the questionnaire must be acknowledged. These limitations suggest caution in interpreting the results and provide directions for our already designed future research endeavors [9].

Concerning future research, this study raises important questions about how perceptions and attitudes of well-being evolve over time in older adults [3,8,9]. Longitudinal and comparative studies in different educational contexts could offer a more comprehensive insight into these aspects.

Continuing from the previous discussion, it is essential to consider the impact of these findings on the existing knowledge in the field [5,6,35]. By challenging or reinforcing previous theories, this study significantly contributes to our understanding of well-being in old age, especially in educational contexts. This comprehensive approach not only enriches existing literature but also guides future research and educational and clinical practices focused on older adults.

Integrated approaches to patient care in the elderly population: An analysis from the perspective of continuing education

Comprehensive patient care, especially in the elderly population, has gained importance in recent decades, recognizing the intersection between various physical, psychological, social, and educational factors that influence quality of life and overall well-being. Within this framework, continuing education emerges as a vital component, offering opportunities to improve psychological well-being and, therefore, the overall health of the elderly. This document explores how the integration of educational programs, focused on lifelong learning, can be part of an integrative approach to patient care, highlighting research conducted at the University for the Elderly in Alicante (Spain).

Intersection between continuing education and comprehensive care

Continuing education has been shown to have a significant impact on the psychological well-being of the elderly, addressing crucial aspects such as self-esteem, self-efficacy, and satisfaction with personal achievements. Participation in educational programs fosters a sense of purpose, enhances cognitive and social skills, and strengthens self-confidence, which is essential for healthy aging. In the context of integrated patient care, these programs not only serve as tools for empowerment and personal development but also as preventive and therapeutic strategies against common age-related problems, such as loneliness, isolation, and cognitive decline.

In this regard, for example, the impact of patient-centered practice in healthcare on the use of wearable devices and the role of this technology in improving patients' mental health has been analyzed [36].

Integrated care model: A holistic approach

The adoption of an integrated care model for the elderly requires multidisciplinary collaboration among health professionals, educators, and community organizations. This model proposes a holistic vision that considers the individual as a whole, recognizing the interdependence between physical, mental, and

social well-being. Continuing education programs, especially designed for this population, should be considered within this model as interventions that significantly contribute to mental and emotional health, complementing medical and rehabilitation interventions.

It is for this reason that the importance and costs of complex biopsychosocial healthcare needs in elderly people are investigated, suggesting the evaluation of interdisciplinary treatment plans [37].

Similarly, the four Italian telemedicine experiences aimed at chronic, geriatric, or partially self-sufficient subjects are noteworthy. The main goal of the OPLON project, supported by the Italian Ministry of Education, Universities, and Research, is to identify and prevent frailty and improve the quality of life of elderly subjects. A general model of tele-monitoring and tele-assistance for frail and pre-frail people with different needs and pathologies is proposed, characterized by three macro-processes (enrollment, assessment, and assistance) and four groups of actors (Patient, general practitioner/specialist physician, multidisciplinary team, and healthcare professionals) [38].

Implementation and challenges

The effective implementation of an integrative approach to patient care faces several challenges, including the need to adapt educational programs to the capabilities and needs of the elderly. It is crucial to develop flexible curricula that allow the active participation of this demographic group, promoting meaningful learning and social interaction. Additionally, it is essential to establish collaboration mechanisms between educational and health institutions to facilitate a coordinated approach that addresses all facets of elderly well-being.

In this sense, for example, the impact of an orthopedic-geriatric continuing education program for nurses on elderly patients who have suffered a hip fracture has been evaluated [39].

Results and potential benefits

The benefits of integrating continuing education into comprehensive patient care are multifaceted. From a mental health perspective, educational programs can mitigate symptoms of depression and anxiety, increase resilience, and promote a positive attitude towards life.

This is how, for example, recent developments in the care of elderly transgender patients are investigated, highlighting the need for appropriate and sensitive care guidelines [40].

In terms of physical health, participation in educational and social activities can lead to a more active lifestyle, reducing the risk of chronic diseases and improving personal autonomy. Additionally, these programs promote social inclusion, combating isolation and promoting community support networks.

Recommendations for practice

To maximize the impact of educational programs within an integrated approach to patient care, it is recommended to:

- Develop personalized educational programs that consider the preferences, abilities, and limitations of the elderly.

- Encourage cross-sector collaboration between educational institutions, health services, and community organizations to create a cohesive and holistic approach to the well-being of the elderly.
- Incorporate assistive technologies and digital platforms to make educational programs accessible to a wider population, especially those with physical limitations or residing in remote areas.
- Regularly evaluate programs to ensure their effectiveness and adaptability to the changing needs of the target population.

CONCLUSION

In our research, we have carefully evaluated the hypotheses and arrived at specific conclusions for each. Regarding the Null Hypothesis, which posits the absence of significant differences in self-reported well-being among different categories of the sample, we have found that it is not fully supported. Our analysis reveals variations in certain aspects of well-being and emotions among different subgroups, especially in relation to age and other demographic factors, suggesting significant differences in some areas of well-being, confirming the rest of the research hypothesis.

Indeed, concerning the first Alternative Hypothesis, proposing the existence of statistically moderate differences in the perception of well-being, our findings support it. We have detected moderate differences in the perception of well-being among participants, particularly in aspects such as confidence in expressing opinions and satisfaction with personal achievements. This reflects moderate variability in well-being perceptions among study participants.

The second Alternative Hypothesis, suggesting statistically significant differences in the perception of well-being among students, is also partially supported by our results. We have observed significant differences in responses to certain questionnaire items, indicating notable variations in self-reported well-being levels among different groups within the sample.

Finally, the third Alternative Hypothesis, related to the internal consistency of the questionnaire items, is only partially fulfilled. The obtained Cronbach's Alpha indicates moderate to low reliability, suggesting that while some items are consistent in measuring the well-being construct, others may not be effectively aligned. However, we have been able to explain and statistically demonstrate this variance in age and the logical contrast of opinions.

Our study focused on exploring the complex interaction between various psychological and social aspects, using a detailed approach to better understand the experiences and perceptions of this population, we have derived important conclusions from it.

Firstly, we observed that a significant proportion of the respondents demonstrate a high level of personal pride and confidence in their opinions, suggesting strong self-esteem and self-efficacy. This finding is noteworthy as it underscores the importance of fostering and maintaining a positive self-image and a confident attitude among older adults, fundamental aspects for their overall well-being.

On the other hand, we have also identified certain challenges,

such as difficulty expressing opinions on controversial topics and susceptibility to others' convictions. These aspects highlight the need to develop communication skills and confidence in this demographic group, something that can be particularly valuable in educational and social environments.

Furthermore, our study has revealed that, while many respondents feel satisfied with their achievements and have a clear direction and goals in life, there is a significant group experiencing disappointment in their personal accomplishments and displaying resistance to change. This indicates the diversity in life experiences and perceptions among older adults, emphasizing the importance of addressing these differences through personalized educational and support programs.

Our findings also highlight the relevance of balancing satisfaction with the past and future with practical competence in handling daily responsibilities. We have observed that the majority of participants effectively manage their daily responsibilities while maintaining a positive outlook on their past and future experiences, a combination that contributes significantly to their overall well-being.

Finally, the relationship between high self-awareness and the desire for personal change has proven to be a particular area of interest. Our results suggest that, while many older adults continue to learn about themselves and maintain an open attitude toward change, they also value stability and consistency in certain aspects of their lives.

Regarding the antagonistic relationship between personal pride and the difficulty expressing opinions, addressing self-esteem and communication skills is crucial. Programs could include workshops that encourage the appreciation of personal achievements and the development of a positive self-image. At the same time, it is crucial to teach effective communication skills and confidence-building to help students express their opinions more easily.

Confidence in one's opinions *versus* external influence requires an approach that strengthens self-confidence and critical thinking. Courses could include activities that promote individual reflection, self-assertion, and the development of a critical and open mindset. This would help students form and trust their own convictions, reducing susceptibility to external influence.

As for satisfaction with personal achievements, it is essential to provide support for managing expectations and redefining goals. This could include counseling sessions and workshops on setting realistic goals and adapting aspirations to each individual's current circumstances and values.

The perception of personal responsibility in the face of disappointment with personal achievements can be enhanced by promoting personal agency and skills for navigating the environment. This could include programs that teach decision-making, adaptability, and strategies to increase self-efficacy.

To address proactivity in personal projects *versus* the cessation of improvement or change attempts, it would be useful to provide training in project management techniques, goal setting, and motivation. For those who have stopped seeking improvements, it would be beneficial to focus on personal development and

motivation through reflection and continuous learning.

High self-awareness and personal growth *versus* resistance to personal change would benefit from strategies that encourage introspection and self-knowledge. Activities such as meditation, reflection, and journal writing can be helpful, as well as workshops focused on self-exploration and identifying areas for personal growth.

In terms of well-being when reflecting on the past and the future, it is important to promote a positive and realistic outlook. This could include strategies to enhance satisfaction with the past and optimism toward the future, along with efficiency in managing daily responsibilities.

Finally, satisfaction with life goals and self-appreciation can be enhanced by reviewing and adjusting goals to be realistic and achievable, and by promoting self-acceptance and the development of a positive self-image. Additionally, for those struggling with managing daily demands and clarity of direction and goals, it would be helpful to provide psychological support and strategies to define and achieve personal goals effectively.

Integrating continuing education into a comprehensive patient care model offers a promising path to improving the quality of life of the elderly. By addressing psychological and emotional well-being through education, it is possible not only to enrich the lives of individuals but also to promote healthy and active aging. Future research should focus on evaluating the long-term impact of these programs and exploring new ways of integration between education and patient care, ensuring a truly holistic approach to the care of the elderly.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors of this study declare that there are no competing interests associated with this research. Each author has carefully examined any potential conflicts of interest, including financial, personal, or professional relationships that could be construed as influencing the research process or its outcomes. After thorough consideration, it has been determined that there are no such interests present. This declaration is made to affirm the objectivity, transparency, and integrity of the research and its findings.

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